

A Bibliometric Analysis of Financial Technologies in the Indian Banking Sector

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Abstract : *The banking industry in India has experienced notable technological progress that has revolutionized its operations and consumer experiences. Using data from 217 publications gathered from the Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus databases, this bibliometric review research investigates how Indian banks are using technology including digital banking, blockchain, artificial intelligence, and fintech advances. Through a thorough analysis of several academic and commercial publications, the report pinpoints important research topics, trends, and the effects of these technologies on productivity, security, and customer satisfaction. The study underscores the significance of technology in propelling financial inclusion and transforming the Indian financial scene, and it also indicates forthcoming avenues for research and innovation in the banking sector.*

Keywords : Bibliometric Analysis, Blockchain, Finance, Fintech, Indian Banking.

1. Introduction

The introduction of modern technology has led to a transformational shift in the Indian banking sector. Global companies have been impacted by the significant interruptions caused by the COVID-19 epidemic and the Russian-Ukrainian war. There has been significant disruption to a number of vital corporate operations, including the global supply chain and financial services (Guo et al., 2024). Through some of the major inventions of the contemporary world, both of these have made a comeback. Following the disruptions, artificial

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intelligence (AI) technologies such as blockchain technology have been essential in revitalizing the banking industry. By enabling traditional financial services to realize their full potential, the implementation of block chain technology has played a pivotal role in propelling the revolutionary expansion of financial technologies, or fintech (Xie et al., 2023). Unfathomable potential has been unlocked in the banking sector through the integration of these digital technologies and the internet.

Fintech is where innovation, information technology (IT), and finance come together (Giglio, 2021). Although there isn't a clear definition for fintech, it often refers to any financial services that have been combined with digital technology. Fintech, according to Mention (2019), includes any innovation aimed at improving financial services delivery, use, and business operations. Fintech uses specialized software and algorithms available on computers and, increasingly, smart phones to help businesses, entrepreneurs, and people manage their finances more efficiently. (Kagan, 2020). New business models can be enabled, automation increased, customer experience improved, financial processes transformed, and decision-making improved through the integration of emerging technology in FinTech.

Financial organizations are better positioned for success in a competitive market because to this integration, which also improves efficiency, security, happiness, innovation, and development (Leong & Sung, 2018). Fintech's future will be shaped by technologies including artificial intelligence (AI), cloud computing, blockchain, Internet of Things (IoT), low- or no-code programming, open source, robots, and machine learning (ML) (Patadiya, 2023). Two significant participants in the fintech industry are emerging markets like China and India (Mention, 2019).

According to the latest report by (Mint, 2023), the US is the country with the most fintech start-ups, followed by the UK. India holds the third position in terms of fintech unicorns. India's fintech market, poised for rapid expansion, surged from \$50 billion in 2021 to an anticipated \$150 billion by 2025, with crucial segments like Payments, Digital Lending, InsurTech, and WealthTech projected to achieve a transaction volume of \$100 trillion and revenue of \$50 billion by 2030 (Invest India, 2024). These reports show India's critical role in the development of fintech. India has a long history with the fintech. Saxena et al. (2022) have highlighted the history of fintech in India. According to the authors, fintech 1.0 started just after independence in 1950, with the nationalization of several Indian banks and increased users of financial services. With the arrival

of the internet and online digital technologies, fintech evolved into fintech 2.0. Online banking, ATMs, and credit cards characterized Fintech 2.0. The emergence of crypto currencies and online wallets, alongside the demonetization movement in 2016, propelled the growth of India's fintech 3.0. With over 2000 fintech firms operating in India, traditional banks were compelled to adapt, incorporating fintech elements into their strategies to cater to tech-savvy customers. Fintech technologies, ranging from crowd funding platforms to mobile payments and robotic investment advisors, have revolutionized the financial industry, driving innovation and reshaping consumer behaviour (Saxena et al., 2022).

There are typically four different types of fintech according to their functions. These are capable of revolutionizing the banking sector. Payment processing and money transfers, investment management, loan origination, and wealth management are the four types that aim to enhance customer experiences and streamline financial processes for banks and individuals alike (Shnaider, 2023). These technologies help improve the loan market, payment services, wealth management, remittance transfers, insurance services, and equity funding (Painoli et al., 2021). New fintech companies bring numerous opportunities to the financial sector, yet some traditional banks are affected by the rapid development of fintech. Fintech companies can make transactions more accessible, reliable, and efficient, and this can disrupt traditional banking methods (Shnaider, 2023).

There are multiple approaches to comprehending a specific scientific domain's evolution and fundamental principles. Various methods, such as quotation analysis for recognizing significant papers and authors, bibliographic coupling for unveiling emerging trends, keyword co-occurrence analysis for charting research domains, and science mapping/network analysis for offering a panoramic view of scientific terrains, along with bibliometric analysis for scrutinizing data associated with scientific literature, contribute to understanding the development and core concepts within a particular field of science (Borregan-Alvarado et al., 2020). One of the most commonly used methods is bibliometric analysis, a rigorous approach to analyzing extensive scientific data (Donthu et al., 2021). With the help of software assistance, a bibliometric analysis can be used to identify relevant research areas, authors, and their relationships by analyzing all published works in a field (Han et al., 2020). Bibliometric analysis depends on recognizing the entire literature, encompassing publications in their most comprehensive scope within a particular subject domain (Ellegaard & Wallin, 2015). The widespread adoption of bibliometric analysis owes to

advancements, accessibility, and the availability of software tools like Gephi, Leximancer, and VOSviewer, in addition to scientific databases like Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) (Donthu et al., 2021). Furthermore, its cross-disciplinary dissemination from information science to business research has contributed to its popularity.

When seeking to comprehend the current status and evolution of a specific topic, bibliometric analysis emerges as one of the most effective options in research. Hence, we conducted a bibliometric analysis to study the state of research on fintech within the Indian banking sector. Before conducting the bibliometric analysis, an extensive literature review revealed that an analysis on this topic is not available in the context of the Indian banking sector. Several bibliometric studies have already been done on fintech and related fields, but none on the Indian banking sector. Pandey et al. (2024) is a bibliometric review of fintech in banking and finance. The authors used the bibliometric and content analysis method on 366 Scopus-indexed publications. This study reveals the existence of a significant opportunity for theoretical and contextual exploration alongside methodological advancements within the fintech literature (Pandey et al., 2024). A bibliometric analysis of fintech trends was conducted by (Garg et al., 2023) by analyzing 665 publications from the Scopus database by evaluating the citation connections among the most influential articles. The research concentrated on examining FinTech's roles and research limitations in digital finance. In the '2023 3rd International Conference on Innovative Practices in Technology and Management (ICIPTM)', a paper on bibliometric and visual analysis of fintech applications is published (Revulagadda et al., 2023). The authors claimed that the leading fintech publishers are in the USA and UK, followed by China. India holds fourth place in terms of fintech-related publications. (Patel et al., 2022) went more specific with their analysis. They specifically studied block chain in banking and finance. As mentioned earlier, block chain is only one of the several technologies used in fintech. On the other hand, our study focuses on fintech as a whole. Rabbani et al. (2022) conducted a bibliometric analysis of crowd funding and P2P lending. These are two of the most critical and innovative financial services of the modern time (Rabbani et al., 2022). Both can be associated with fintech since they represent innovative financial services technology enables. This study focused on fintech and its functions in India's banking sector.

By conducting a bibliometric analysis on this topic, we identified areas within fintech in Indian banking that have received less attention or remain unexplored. This can guide future research efforts, enabling researchers to focus on filling

these gaps and contributing meaningfully to the field. By examining citation counts, publication trends, and research collaboration patterns, we could map these studies' relevance to the field. Insights from this study can inform policymakers and industry stakeholders about the prevailing research landscape in fintech and its implications for the Indian banking sector. This knowledge can guide the formulation of policies, strategic decisions, and investments to foster innovation and competitiveness in the industry. Lastly, a bibliometric analysis can contribute to the academic discourse by adding to the body of scholarly literature and laying the groundwork for future research endeavours in fintech and banking in the Indian context.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 offers a detailed overview of the methods and data employed in the study. Section 3, the results section, will analyze and interpret the findings derived from the software. This section will include visual representations and thorough descriptions of the results. Section 4 will delve into discussions surrounding the interpreted results and outline potential avenues for future research. The concluding remarks on the study will be presented in the final section.

2. Methodology

This study was conducted through a meticulously structured three-phase process. In the study's first phase, we collected data for the relevant articles. WoS, named the Web of Science initially and established by Eugene Garfield in the 1960s, is the pioneering bibliographic database (Pranckutė, 2021). Several comparative studies of these two databases are available (Martín-Martín et al., 2018; Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016; Pranckutė, 2021; Zhu & Liu, 2020). Our research incorporates Scopus and WoS databases, recognizing that each possesses distinct advantages and drawbacks, ensuring comprehensive coverage of high-quality works in the field. After the search, we identified 173 and 54 documents from Scopus and WoS, respectively. After combining and removing the ten duplicate articles, we ended up with 217 relevant articles to our study.

The second step involved an analysis of the 217 papers that had been nominated. The analysis was undertaken to better understand the topic's publication frequency, effect in academic disciplines, and change over time. Biblioshiny and VoS Viewer's multiple presentation choices enable deep investigation of bibliometric maps, allowing users to precisely expose many elements of the data (van Eck & Waltman, 2010). These technologies work together to allow for more in-depth study and interpretation of bibliometric data.

Figure-1 : Flowchart of Data Collection Process

The third and final step is the reporting of bibliometric analysis. Reporting any research is very critical. Through reporting, the quality and validity of the analysis can be assessed, contributing to the advancement of knowledge in the field. Additionally, it provides researchers with recognition and facilitates informed decision-making for policy, practice, and further research directions.

3. Results

3.1. Publication Analysis

At first, we focus on assessing the quantity and impact of scientific publications; including citation metrics, core sources, authors' productivity, and affiliations' contributions over time. By focusing on these key metrics, we can effectively evaluate scientific research's quantity, impact, and dissemination channels and recognize influential authors, affiliations, and documents within the research landscape. This approach ensures a comprehensive yet focused analysis of publication dynamics.

3.1.1. Annual Scientific Production

As illustrated in Table-1, there has been a substantial increase in the volume of publications on this topic in India. After analyzing the data acquired from Scopus and WoS, we noticed a steady increase in the production volume since 2020. The most noticeable change occurred during the 2021-22 period. There is an increase of more than 60% in the annual production in 2022 compared to 2021.

Table-1 : Annual Production of the Last 10 Years

Year	Articles
2014	8
2015	7
2016	15
2017	6
2018	10
2019	17
2020	13
2021	15
2022	39
2023	46
2024	11

Figure-2 shows the average citations over the years. The graph also has a very prominent peak during the year 2020. This is the year with the most production; hence, it is evident that it will also mark the most citations. When we analyze the trend of citations over the years, a general upward movement can be seen despite the ups and downs in the graph. With India’s new technology adoption measures, we can expect more studies on Fintech and associated technologies coming from India in the latter part of 2024 and the coming years.

Figure-2 : Average Citations over the Years

3.1.2. Most Relevant Sources

It is not unexpected that a financial journal leads the pack regarding article count. The Indian Journal of Finance shares the top spot with the International Journal of Applied Engineering Research, each boasting six articles. Communications in Computer and Information Science, Smart Innovation Systems and Technologies, and Sustainability have four articles each. Table-2 outlines the top 10 journals and their respective publication totals.

Table-2 : Journals and their Share of Articles

Sources	Articles
Indian Journal of Finance	6
International Journal of Applied Engineering Research	6
Communications in Computer and Information Science	4
Smart Innovation Systems and Technologies	4
Sustainability	4
AIP Conference Proceedings	3
Global Business Review	3
International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology	3
International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research	3
International Journal of Bank Marketing	3

3.1.3. Most Relevant Authors

Figure-3 displays the top 10 authors based on the number of publications. Singh S, Gupta S, and Sharma S are leading the list, with eight, six, and five publications, respectively. Notably, with a publication dating back to 2016, Kumar A is the longest-active author among the top ten. The graph focuses solely on currently active authors and does not assess their impact on the research community.

Chitkara University is the most relevant institution in the analyzed dataset, contributing eight articles. Following closely behind, four universities share the second position, each contributing five articles. Figure-4 depicts the top 10 affiliations based on their total number of publications.

Figure-3 : Most Relevant Authors by Publications

3.2. Keywords Analysis

In this section, we analyzed the textual content of publications, examining the frequency and trends of specific words, co-occurrence networks, and thematic mapping to identify prevalent topics and their evolution over time. Pesta et al. (2018) emphasized the significance of studying keywords. Keywords play a vital role in grasping the popularity of a particular research topic (Pesta et al., 2018). Since all the articles we used for this study focused on the Indian Banking sector, India became the most common keyword in the analysis. However, we should focus on the rest of the keywords in the table to understand the characteristics of the research topic. Block chain, e-banking, and mobile banking are some of the vital keywords to be noted.

Figures-4 present visual representations of the keywords. Figure-4 is a tree map illustrating the relevant keywords. According to Long et al. (2017), tree maps are practical tools for visually representing hierarchical data. They portray each node as a rectangle, further subdivided for child nodes, ensuring efficient use of space and aiding pattern identification, especially when colour and size variations align with the tree structure. Tree maps facilitate the clear display of thousands of items on a screen simultaneously, making them valuable for data visualization tasks (Long et al., 2017). Figure-5, the Keyword co-occurrence

3.3. Thematic Analysis

A thematic map aids in comprehending the evolution of the research field. Figure-6 depicts the thematic map of our analysis, providing insights into the interconnectedness and evolution of various themes within the research domain. It is a two-dimensional map divided into four quadrants (Thangavel & Chandra, 2023). As illustrated in the graph, we observe distinct thematic categories: niche themes, motor themes, basic themes, and emerging or declining themes. According to Muñoz-Leiva et al. (2012), keywords within niche themes hold only marginal significance. Conversely, the motor themes section comprises the most relevant and well-developed keywords within the research field. These keywords represent established and clearly defined aspects of the domain. Meanwhile, themes in the basic themes quadrant indicate a developmental stage but hold significant importance for the research field’s progress. Lastly, the quadrant representing emerging or declining themes contains keywords with limited developmental potential.(Muñoz-Leiva et al., 2012).

Figure-6 : Thematic Evolution

Figure-7 : A Conceptual Map of Factorial Analysis

4. Discussions

This bibliometric analysis aimed to assess the current state of research on fintech in the Indian banking sector. In total, 217 papers authored by 511 individuals were examined. The subject demonstrated an annual growth rate of 6.51%, with a notable increase in researcher interest over the past seven years. Despite this growth, publications have remained relatively steady since 2016. These 217 studies were dispersed across 165 sources, indicating a lack of concentrated focus on the subject within a single publication outlet. With a contribution of 8 articles each, the Indian Journal of Finance and the International Journal of Applied Engineering Research emerged as the top two journals regarding publication volume. However, it is worth noting that only the former exhibited a high impact score, whereas the latter had a comparatively low h-index score.

When analyzing the number of publications per author, it was found that the highest contribution from a single author amounted to 8 out of the 217 articles studied. This suggests a lack of sustained interest from many authors, with only a few, such as Singh S and Kumar A, demonstrating consistent engagement over time. This indicates that many authors may not be continuously involved in studying the subject. Additionally, over 95% of the articles analyzed were single-

country publications. While these studies focus solely on India, collaboration with foreign authors could enhance research outcomes by facilitating comparisons of technologies across different countries. Similarly, the analysis of affiliations revealed the participation of several organizations, with the most productive affiliation contributing eight articles. This underscores the broad reach of the field under discussion but also suggests that studies have only scratched the surface, emphasizing the need for more focused research to understand the subject area truly.

Throughout the analysis, several keywords were identified that provide insight into the field's evolution over time. Notably, "India" emerged as the most frequently occurring keyword, which aligns with the focus on the Indian banking sector in our study. Interestingly, only "block chain" appeared in the top ten keywords, which can be considered a technology used in fintech. This suggests that research on other technologies like IoT, ML, cloud computing, and robotics is still in its early stages and presents opportunities for exploration for new researchers. Additionally, keywords such as "e-banking" and "mobile banking" were among the top ten, highlighting their significance as fintech applications. However, ample room remains for further investigation into practical fintech applications, including credit score computing, fraud detection, and wealth management. Researchers are encouraged to delve into these areas to enhance understanding and knowledge in the field.

The thematic map revealed several influential and emerging themes in the analysis. Among the most significant themes were deep learning, machine learning, digital banking, financial inclusion, and fintech. Additionally, themes such as financial literacy, mobile banking, online banking, financial performance, and technology acceptance models emerged as new focus areas, showing potential for future growth. Over time, specific themes have evolved. While banking has become less prominent, finance has grown more than in previous years. On the other hand, the evolution of electronic money appears to have been less significant over time. These observations underscore the dynamic nature of research themes within the fintech domain and highlight areas ripe for further exploration and development.

The bibliometric analysis provides a comprehensive overview of the current state of fintech research in the Indian banking sector. While the findings indicate a growing interest and investment in the subject, there remain opportunities for further exploration and collaboration to deepen understanding and drive meaningful impact. There is a need for sustained research efforts to deepen

understanding and address gaps in knowledge, particularly in underexplored areas. Fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and international partnerships can enrich research outcomes and facilitate knowledge transfer across borders. By leveraging diverse expertise and resources, researchers can generate more comprehensive insights into the complexities of fintech adoption and its impact on the Indian banking ecosystem. Lastly, as the field continues to evolve, it is essential to remain vigilant of emerging trends and technological advancements. Future research should strive to stay abreast of developments in artificial intelligence, data analytics, and cyber security, as these factors will increasingly shape the trajectory of fintech innovation in India. By leveraging insights from this analysis, researchers can chart a course for future investigations to advance knowledge and promote innovation in fintech within the Indian context.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, the bibliometric analysis of fintech research within the Indian banking sector offers valuable insights into its growth trends, publication landscape, author contributions, thematic evolution, and potential future directions. The analysis revealed a steady annual growth rate, indicating increasing interest in fintech research over the past years. Comparatively, more journals have contributed to this area, but the dominance of a single source cannot be found. This analysis also helped us to reveal the prominent themes under development in this field. Understanding the evolution of these themes provides valuable insights into the shifting focus of fintech research over time.

In light of these findings, future research efforts should prioritize interdisciplinary collaboration, international partnerships, and exploration of emerging themes to advance understanding and drive innovation in fintech within the Indian banking sector. By addressing gaps in knowledge and leveraging insights from thematic analysis, researchers can contribute to the continued growth and development of fintech research, ultimately benefiting the broader banking ecosystem and society.

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